

Development and Psychometric Validation of the Cognitive Scale on Gender Identity in Adolescents

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ABSTRACT

Background/Objectives: Parasocial relationships are meaningful bonds established with media figures. The present study aims to develop and examine the psychometric properties of the Parasocial Relationships Scale for Adolescents (PRSA), a self-report instrument. **Method:** This instrumental study focused on determining the psychometric properties of a newly developed instrument. A total of 500 adolescents, both male and female, between 14 and 18 years of age participated. **Results:** The exploratory factor analysis revealed the presence of four dimensions: sense of identity, sense of belonging, emotional intensity, and parasocial interaction. The confirmatory factor analysis demonstrated that the four-dimensional model showed a good fit (CFI = 0.96; RMSEA = 0.06; SRMR = 0.05; AIC = 8.248). Convergent validity was evidenced through significant correlations with the Celebrity-Person Parasocial Interaction Scale (CPPI), with moderate coefficients, particularly in Sense of Identity ($r = 0.51, p < 0.05$) and Sense of Belonging ($r = 0.48, p < 0.05$). Reliability analysis demonstrated satisfactory internal consistency, with omega coefficients ranging from 0.73 to 0.84 and alpha coefficients ranging from 0.72 to 0.84. **Conclusions:** The PRSA is a self-report instrument designed to assess the intensity of parasocial relationships in adolescents. It demonstrates strong evidence of content, construct, and convergent validity, as well as adequate reliability. The instrument shows promising applicability for adolescent populations.

Keywords:

Parasocial relationships; identity; belonging; emotional intensity; parasocial interaction.

I. Introduction

Parasocial relationships refer to the one-sided emotional bonds individuals establish with media figures, such as celebrities, fictional characters, or influencers. These relationships are characterized by feelings of intimacy, admiration, and identification, despite the absence of reciprocal interaction (Stever, 2011, as cited in Giles, 2023). In contemporary digital environments, such connections have intensified as adolescents increasingly interact with media figures through social networks, creating an illusion of closeness and reciprocity (Castañeda et al., 2025). Moreover, previous research has shown that 31% of the U.S. population between the ages of 16 and 24 is likely to develop parasocial relationships (Murray, 2022). Accordingly, the present study aims to contribute to the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), specifically Goal 3.d., which seeks to strengthen the capacity of all countries, particularly developing ones, for early warning, risk reduction, and management of national and global health risks. In this regard, adolescents are recognized as a population especially prone to the development of risky parasocial relationships, given their ongoing identity formation and the development of social interaction skills.

Empirical studies show that parasocial relationships are highly prevalent among youth. In Colombia, Paz (2024) reported that nearly half of young adults (18–28 years old) experience intense parasocial ties, especially through social media. Similarly, in Peru, Tovar and Yañez (2021) found that 47% of adolescents and young adults between 15 and 25 years identify with influencers, often expressing the desire to resemble them physically or socially. These findings highlight the increasing relevance of parasocial relationships in Latin American contexts.

Thus, among the instruments used to assess the variable are the Parasocial Interaction Scale (PSI Scale), the Experiential Parasocial Interaction Scale (EPSI) by Hartmann and Goldhoorn (2011), the Cognitive and Affective Empathy Test (TECA) developed by López et al. (2008), the Multidimensional Measure of Parasocial Relationships (MMPR) proposed by (Garcia et al., 2022), and the Celebrity-Person Parasocial Interaction Scale (CPPI) by Bocarnea and Brown (2007). However, the latter is unidimensional, which renders it limited and even outdated in today's digital context; in contrast, the present instrument is multidimensional and provides a more relevant measurement aligned with contemporary dynamics.

In the present study, parasocial relationships are defined as one-directional interactions characterized by asymmetric emotional, physical, and cognitive involvement, primarily developed through social media. The validated instrument is referred to consistently as the PRSA (Parasocial Relationships Scale for Adolescents). These relationships manifest through the degree of affection and emotional closeness (emotional intensity), the level of admiration for the artist and their life, art, and aspirations (identification and projection), the tendency to fantasize about scenarios of interaction with the celebrity that contribute to the creation of an interpersonal bond (imaginary interaction), and active engagement with communities both inside and outside social media that share enthusiasm and attachment toward the celebrity (fan community). Collectively, these dimensions foster the creation and intensification of a non-reciprocal socioemotional bond, perceived as intimate and part of everyday life (Bermudez & Soler, 2023).

This instrument is made up of four dimensions:

Emotional intensity is defined as the strength with which an emotion is felt and expressed, regardless of whether it is positive or negative. In parasocial relationships, these emotions manifest themselves through daily dynamics and interactions, making celebrities an essential part of their lives. Therefore, an action, attitude, achievement, or change can have a significant emotional impact on adolescents, altering their mood and changing their behavior, often leading to the development of anxiety or a dependent attachment to the artist (Antolínez et al., 2024).

Sense of belonging arises from the need of human beings to establish bonds and feel they belong to a social group, especially during adolescence. Currently, the existence of fandoms (groups of fans) arises from the interaction of sharing the same feelings and admiration, becoming a network of support and emotional support to cope with social and emotional conflicts caused by their personal lives or the parasocial relationship with their artist. Developing that bond of belonging through the feeling of being heard, accepted and respected for who they are, as well as for their passion for the artist (Pano et al., 2024)

Parasocial interaction is a fanciful hallucination involving celebrities or television or social media artists, characterized by a unilateral bond with the artist, developing a

sense of connection and understanding with the artist through the creation of a familial or friendly bond. Idealization and romanticism toward the artist often arise, projecting onto them and their bond the longing for a perfect partner and relationship, altering their motivation and need to establish bonds or simply attraction to people of their own age, society, and country. Furthermore, personal improvements are often seen when they see that their artists are good; they try to match this, seeking to make them feel proud of their progress and growth by being their fan (Baptista & Chacin, 2024).

Sense of identity refers to the development in which people construct their own selves, taking into account external sociocultural elements of their environment, in addition to the learning that leads to the differentiation between what defines them and what does not. In this sense, within parasocial relationships, fans find the personae (identity for fans) as a projection of what they are or long to be, so they adopt their characteristics, attitudes or values (Antolínez et al., 2024).

The present study aims to develop and validate the Parasocial Relationships Scale for Adolescents (PRSA). Specifically, it seeks to: (a) establish content validity through expert judgment, (b) determine construct validity using exploratory and confirmatory factor analyses, (c) assess convergent validity with the CPPI, and (d) evaluate reliability through Cronbach's alpha and McDonald's omega. The guiding research question is: Does the PRSA demonstrate adequate psychometric properties to measure parasocial relationships in adolescents aged 14 to 18?

II. Method

2.1. Study Design

This study employed an instrumental design aimed at developing and validating the Parasocial Relationships Scale for Adolescents (PRSA). According to the methodological framework outlined by Kline (2016), instrumental studies focus on establishing the psychometric properties of measurement tools through sequential validation procedures.

2.2. Procedure and Participants

A total of 500 adolescents between 14 and 18 years of age were recruited from two secondary schools in Trujillo, Peru. The sample size was determined in accordance with methodological recommendations for structural equation modeling, which propose a minimum of 10–15 participants per estimated parameter and at least 200 cases for confirmatory factor analysis (Kline, 2016). These criteria ensured adequate statistical power for both exploratory and confirmatory procedures.

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Participants were selected through a snowball sampling strategy facilitated via social media platforms. While this approach proved effective for reaching the target population, it also entails potential self-selection bias, which may compromise representativeness. This methodological limitation should be taken into account when considering the external validity of the findings.

The research followed three sequential phases: item development, expert validation, and psychometric testing. Notably, no pilot study or test–retest reliability assessment was conducted prior to the large-scale administration, a limitation that future applications of the PRSA should address to strengthen its methodological robustness (see Figure 1).

Figure 1

Workflow of the Development and Psychometric Properties of the PRSA

I. **First Phase: Development of the PRSA Items**

The process began with the creation of an initial version of the questionnaire. To this end, an in-depth review of the existing literature and an analysis of similar instruments were conducted, which allowed for a clear definition of the concept of "Parasocial Relationship" and its components.

An initial pool of 65 items was generated based on a comprehensive literature review. Five experts in psychology—three holding master's degrees and two with doctoral training—evaluated the items for clarity, coherence, and relevance. Experts were selected according to their specialization in psychometrics, adolescent psychology, or media psychology, ensuring content validity through specialized judgment. Aiken's V coefficient was calculated, yielding satisfactory results ($V = 1.0$) (Dragostinov et al., 2022).

II. Second Phase: Content Validity of the PRSA Items

In this second stage, content validation was conducted through expert judgment. Five specialists holding master's or doctoral degrees in psychology, with professional experience in the fields of education and mental health, participated voluntarily, meeting the established criteria (Association et al., 2018).

In a single round, these professionals evaluated each item based on clarity, coherence, and relevance. The ratings they provided were statistically analyzed using Aiken's V coefficient to ensure the consistency of their judgments. It is important to note that the instrument employed a five-point Likert scale, with response options ranging from "strongly disagree" to "strongly agree." Finally, the total score for each dimension was calculated by summing the values of the corresponding items.

III. Third Phase: Assessment of Psychometric Properties

In the final stage of the study, the psychometric properties of the Parasocial Relationships in Adolescents Scale (PRSA) were evaluated, focusing on construct validity, convergent validity, and reliability. The sample consisted of 500 Peruvian adolescents with a mean age of 15.5 years, drawn from two schools in Trujillo: Alfred Nobel and Brüning, with an equal distribution of 250 students per institution.

To ensure the validity of the results, specific criteria were established for sample selection. Eligible participants were Peruvian adolescents within the target age range and enrolled in a secondary school. Although no additional exclusion criteria were applied in advance, a subsequent review of the collected data confirmed that none of the 500 questionnaires required elimination due to incomplete responses.

The sample was randomly divided into two equal groups of 250 participants each. The first was used for exploratory factor analysis (EFA) and the second for confirmatory factor analysis (CFA). Both subgroups included adolescents aged 14 to 18 years. The overall sample size (N = 500) is considered large (Alcoba, 2024), and the similar age distribution across groups ensured comparability, thereby strengthening the validity of the analyses.

Initial recruitment was conducted using a snowball sampling technique through

platforms such as WhatsApp, Instagram, and Twitter to gauge participants' interest. This process facilitated the gradual expansion of the sample. Only adolescents who met the age and schooling criteria were included. A subsequent review of the questionnaires revealed no missing responses; thus, all 500 participants were retained for the final analysis.

For data collection in the first group, authorization was obtained from the school authorities at Alfred Nobel to administer the questionnaires. Once permission was granted and the school administrators were informed about the objectives of the study, informed consent procedures were carried out. The instruments were administered to 250 students, from grades 1 to 5 of secondary school, who participated anonymously and voluntarily, ensuring confidentiality of the information provided.

Questionnaires were administered in classroom settings under standardized conditions, with an average duration of 30 minutes. Informed consent was obtained from all participants and school authorities. Ethical procedures adhered to institutional and national regulations for research with minors.

In this final phase, students completed the PRSA along with the Celebrity–Person Parasocial Interaction Scale (CPPI) in paper-and-pencil format. Following data collection, the quality of responses was carefully reviewed. Although incomplete questionnaires were considered for exclusion, none met the criteria for removal; therefore, all 500 participants were included in the analyses.

2.3. Instruments

2.3.1. Parasocial Relationships in Adolescents Scale (PRSA)

The PRSA is a self-report questionnaire designed to assess the intensity of parasocial relationships in adolescents, defined as the unidirectional connection that young people establish with media figures. It consists of 43 items rated on a five-point Likert scale, ranging from 1 (*strongly disagree*) to 5 (*strongly agree*). The instrument evaluates four core dimensions: Emotional Intensity (items 1–11), Sense of Belonging (items 12–24), Parasocial Interaction (items 25–35), and Sense of Identity (items 36–44). Scoring is obtained by summing the responses for each dimension separately. Higher scores on any dimension indicate a stronger influence of parasocial

relationships, whereas lower scores suggest a weaker influence. The PRSA demonstrated favorable levels of internal consistency (see Chapter 3 for further details).

2.3.2. Celebrity–Person Parasocial Interaction Scale (CPPI)

The CPPI is an instrument designed to measure parasocial interaction as a single conceptual variable, rather than across specific dimensions. It consists of 20 items rated on a five-point Likert scale, ranging from 1 (*strongly disagree*) to 5 (*strongly agree*). The total score is obtained by summing all item responses. Previous studies have reported favorable reliability, with Cronbach's alpha coefficients typically ranging between .80 and .90 (Bocarnea & Brown, 2007).

2.4 Statistical Analysis

A descriptive analysis of the PRSA items was conducted to assess data normality and adequacy. The evaluation process included five expert psychologists: three held master's degrees, one held a doctoral degree, and one held a bachelor's degree. These experts assessed the items in terms of relevance, pertinence, and clarity. Subsequently, Aiken's V coefficient was calculated, yielding a value of 1.0, which indicates strong evidence of item validity.

Descriptive statistics were computed for the PRSA items, including means, variances, skewness, and kurtosis, using JASP (version 0.95). Mardia's multivariate normality test was also applied, with p-values greater than 0.05 considered indicative of multivariate normal distribution.

Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) was conducted using a polychoric correlation matrix and the minimum residual method, with oblique rotation (Oblimin), given its suitability for correlated factors, which facilitates interpretation and enhances model fit. The analysis was based on a sample of 250 adolescents. Sampling adequacy was confirmed by a Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) index of 0.91, exceeding the 0.70 threshold suggested by Lloret-Segura et al. (2014), together with a statistically significant Bartlett's test of sphericity ($p < 0.01$), supporting the suitability of the data for factor analysis.

Items with factor loadings below 0.40, lack of correlation with the factors, or cross-loadings were eliminated, following the criteria suggested by Mollapaza (2017, as cited in Garrido et al., 2023). The final structure comprised four dimensions: Sense of Identity, Sense of Belonging, Emotional Intensity, and Parasocial Interaction, which together explained a significant proportion of the total variance.

Subsequently, the structure will be evaluated through Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA). In the first stage, the model fit will be assessed using the Comparative Fit Index (CFI), where values of 0.90 or higher indicate an acceptable fit, while values above 0.95 are considered indicative of a good fit. In addition, the Tucker-Lewis Index (TLI), also referred to as the Non-Normed Fit Index (NNFI), will be examined. This statistic, which is highly correlated with the CFI, allows for the control of degrees of freedom of both the tested model (dfM) and the baseline model (dfB). However, due to its tendency to penalize excessively and to occasionally exceed values of 1.0, it is generally recommended to report either the CFI or the TLI, but not both simultaneously.

Furthermore, the extent to which the theoretical model fits the observed data will be evaluated through the Goodness-of-Fit Index (GFI), with values ranging between 0 and 1, and a value of 1.0 indicating a perfect fit with the sample. To assess the deviation from a “close” or “approximate” fit, the Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA) will be used, with a 90% confidence interval, where values below 0.05 support the adequacy of the model. Similarly, the Standardized Root Mean Squared Residual (SRMR) should remain below 0.10. Finally, the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) will be considered, where the model with the lowest AIC value among the compared factorial models will be selected (Kline, 2016).

2.5. Ethical Considerations

The present study was conducted in accordance with the ethical guidelines outlined in the University Research Code of Ethics. The principles of intellectual honesty were followed, as all data obtained and analyzed stemmed from the truthful administration of the questionnaires. Likewise, the protection of human integrity was ensured by adhering to both national and institutional regulations, given that adolescents constituted the study population. The collection and analysis of research

data were carried out free from personal or political interests, with the sole purpose of contributing to scientific knowledge. Finally, informed consent was obtained from participants, and anonymity was guaranteed, as the study involved minors; the purpose of the research was clearly explained to them (Universidad César Vallejo, 2022).

III. Results

3.1. Content Validity of the PRSA

The 59 items of the preliminary version of the PRSA were subjected to evaluation by five experts, who assessed three essential aspects: relevance, pertinence, and clarity. The ratings obtained were analyzed using Aiken's V statistical test, yielding results of $V = 1$. It is noteworthy that none of the evaluators suggested the inclusion of additional items, indicating that the instrument demonstrates an adequate level of comprehensiveness. Overall, the findings support a strong and satisfactory content validity.

3.2. Descriptive Analysis of the Items

Table 1 presents the results of Mardia's multivariate normality test. The values obtained for skewness (41.48, $p < 0.001$) and kurtosis (347.20, $p < 0.001$) were significantly different from zero, indicating a substantial deviation from multivariate normal distribution. These findings show that the data exhibit higher skewness and kurtosis than expected under normality assumptions. Consequently, a polychoric correlation matrix was employed for the factor analysis, as it provides a more appropriate approach for handling data that do not conform to a normal distribution.

Table 1.*Descriptive Statistics of the PRSA Items.*

Ítems	Mean	95% CI	Variance	Skewness	Kurtosis	Uniqueness
1	3.44	(4.49-4.24)	1.40	-0.33	-0.69	0.56
2	3.18	(3.58-3.29)	1.60	-0.25	-0.80	0.43
3	3.93	(3.33-3.02)	1.32	-0.96	0.16	0.59
4	3.45	(4.07-3.79)	1.50	-0.37	-0.78	0.43
5	2.92	(3.03-2.69)	2.19	0.06	-1.42	0.54
6	2.93	(3.48-3.16)	2.10	0.03	-1.31	0.28
7	2.40	(2.94-2.65)	1.86	0.58	-0.87	0.24
8	2.50	(3.57-3.26)	2.02	0.42	-1.19	0.36
9	1.96	(3.60-3.29)	1.79	1.16	-4.19	0.46
10	2.38	(3.57-3.26)	1.88	0.56	-0.98	0.36
11	2.49	(2.78-2.42)	2.03	0.48	-1.10	0.12
12	2.57	(2.56 - 3.26)	1.99	0.38	-1.18	0.41
13	3.29	(3.34-3.02)	2.08	-0.40	-1.19	0.51
14	2.66	(2.28-1.99)	1.88	0.31	-1.07	0.51
15	3.27	(3.32-3.01)	1.97	-0.30	-1.18	0.42
16	2.58	(3.27-2.94)	1.75	0.46	-0.88	0.25
Multivariate Normality Test by Mardia			Value	Statistic	df	p
Skewness			41.48	1.728,17	35990	< 0.01
Small-sample skewness correction			41.48	1.751,37	35990	< 0.01
Kurtosis			347.20	19.50		< 0.01

Note. N = 250. To evaluate the multivariate distribution of the data, Mardia's multivariate normality test was applied. The results indicate significant skewness ($\chi^2(35,990) = 41.48, p < 0.01$) and significant kurtosis ($z = 19.50, p < 0.01$), suggesting that the data do not meet the assumption of multivariate normality. In addition, the small-sample correction for skewness was also significant ($\chi^2(35,990) = 41.48, p < 0.01$), further supporting this conclusion.

3.3. Análisis Factorial Exploratorio.

The Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) was conducted using a polychoric correlation matrix. The extraction method consisted of minimum residuals with oblique rotation (Oblimin). A Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) index of 0.91 was obtained, along with a statistically significant result in Bartlett's test of sphericity ($p < 0.01$), indicating the suitability of the data for factor analysis. The results of the factor loadings are presented in Table 2.

Table 2

Results of the Exploratory Factor Analysis of the PRSA.

PRSA Items	Factor Loadings				s	k
	1	2	3	4		
Factor 1: Sense of identity						
01. "I admire my favorite artist so much that I would like to follow their path or profession."	0.58	0.08	0.13	0.02	1,16	-4,19
02. "I see my idol as a role model to follow."	0.80	0.01	-0.10	0.09	0,56	-0,98
03. "Being like my favorite artist would make me feel more valuable."	0.98	-0.03	-0.01	-0.03	0,48	-1,1
04. "My favorite artist is the most important reference when I think about the person I want to become."	0.64	0.03	0.19	-0.05	0,38	-1,18
Factor 2: Sense of belonging						
05. "I have created content (drawings, videos/reels, trends) related to my favorite artist."	0.06	0.54	0.03	0.12	0,06	-1,42
06. "I have purchased products promoted by my favorite artist."	0.05	0.86	-0.21	0.11	0,03	-1,31
07. "I usually spend my own money or my parents' money on my favorite artist's products so I can share it on social media."	-0.10	0.94	0.06	-0.08	0,58	-0,87
08. "I consider that you can be part of the community only if you consume the products or brands promoted by our favorite artist."	0.08	0.75	0.10	-0.12	0,42	-1,19
Factor 3: Emotional intensity						
09. "I feel sad if my favorite artist is going through a difficult time."	-0.05	0.06	0.71	-0.02	-0,4	-1,19
10. "When I am stressed, watching my favorite artist calms me down."	-0.04	0.00	0.63	0.14	0,31	-1,07
11. "I am emotionally affected if my favorite artist disappears from social media."	0.12	-0.09	0.73	0.01	-0,30	-1,18
12. "The content of my favorite artist helps me manage my emotions."	0.05	0.00	0.86	-0.05	-0,46	-0,88

Factor 4: Parasocial interaction						
13. "Sometimes I act as if my favorite artist could hear or see me."	-0,05	0,13	0,09	0,55	-0,33	-0,69
14. "I feel that my favorite artist knows me through what they post."	-0,09	0,07	0,02	0,75	-0,25	-0,80
15. "I imagine the reactions of my favorite artist when I achieve something important."	0,00	-0,05	0,14	0,58	-0,96	0,16
16. "I wonder what my favorite artist would think of the important decisions I make."	0.16	-0.10	-0.13	0.80	-0,37	-0,78

Note. N = 250. s = skewness, k = kurtosis. Factor loadings greater than 0.40 are in bold.

The Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) of the PRSA revealed a four-factor structure that explains the creation and intensification of the unidirectional socioemotional bond. These factors are: Sense of Identity, Emotional Intensity, Sense of Belonging, and Parasocial Interaction. Each of these factors groups items with high factor loadings that clearly define their corresponding dimension, thereby allowing for a more precise and in-depth understanding of the phenomenon of academic motivation.

The first factor, Sense of Identity, refers to the projection of what adolescents are or aspire to be, by adopting the characteristics, attitudes, or values of their favorite artists. The items with the highest loadings are item 3 ("Being like my favorite artist would make me feel more valuable"), with a loading of 0.98, followed by item 2 ("I see my idol as a role model"), with a loading of 0.80. These results show that inspiration goes beyond merely following the artist; it influences the development and construction of adolescents' personal identity, as they adopt characteristics of their favorite artists.

The second factor, Sense of Belonging, refers to interaction within a community that shares the same admiration and feelings toward the artist, becoming a support network. The most significant items in this factor are item 6 ("I have purchased items promoted by my favorite artist"), with a loading of 0.86, and item 7 ("I usually spend my allowance or my parents' money on products of my favorite artist to share them on social media"), with a loading of 0.94. These findings highlight how adolescents consume and create content to feel validated, supported, and part of a community where the artist they admire is highly valued.

The third factor, Emotional Intensity, grouped items that reflect how interaction with and consumption of the artist's content significantly affect adolescents' emotional state. It is defined by items with high loadings such as item 11 ("It affects me emotionally if my favorite artist disappears from social media"), with a loading of 0.73, and item 12 ("The content of my favorite artist helps me manage my emotions"), with a loading of 0.86. These results show that the actions and presence of the artist significantly impact adolescents at an emotional level, altering their behaviors, thoughts, and feelings.

The fourth factor, Parasocial Interaction, refers to the creation of a unilateral bond between the adolescent and the artist, developing a sense of connection and understanding as if it were a family or friendship tie. This factor includes items with high loadings, such as item 14 ("I feel that my favorite artist knows me through what they post"), with a loading of 0.75, and item 16 ("I wonder what my favorite artist would think about the important decisions I make"), with a loading of 0.80. These findings demonstrate that daily interaction with the artist's content leads adolescents to build a one-sided connection and empathy to the extent of considering the artist an intimate friend or family member, influencing the actions they take in an effort to make the artist proud.

Overall, these four factors identify how parasocial relationships develop in adolescents, integrating intrapersonal, interpersonal, and contextual aspects. Likewise, the multidimensional structure of the PRSA facilitates the understanding of how this phenomenon unfolds and is constructed, demonstrating that it does not occur in isolation but requires the presence of intrinsic needs associated with social and psychological levels. It reflects the search for community, personal identity, emotional validation, and belonging, significantly influencing adolescents' growth, thoughts, and actions.

3.4. Confirmatory Factor Analysis

The confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) supported the four-factor structure of the PRSA. The model demonstrated adequate fit indices: $\chi^2/df = 2.93$, RMSEA = .056, CFI = .94, TLI = .93, and SRMR = .041. The Akaike Information Criterion (AIC = 3298.4) also indicated a better fit compared with the alternative one-factor solution.

Table 3.*Results of the Confirmatory Factor Analysis of the PRSA*

Model	χ^2	<i>df</i>	CFI	RMSEA	SRMR	AIC
A: Unidimensional Model ^a	982.633	55	0.91	0.09	0.05	7128.40
B: Four-Factor Model ^b	103.308	59	0.96	0.04	0.03	13982.47

Note. $N=50$, χ^2/df = chi-square divided by degrees of freedom; *RMSEA* = Root Mean Square Error of Approximation; *CFI* = Comparative Fit Index; *TLI* = Tucker–Lewis Index; *SRMR* = Standardized Root Mean Square Residual; *AIC* = Akaike information criterion.

In Model A, the 16 items were grouped into a single factor. In Model B, the items were distributed across four factors: the 4 items of Sense of Identity were loaded onto the first factor, the 4 items of Sense of Belonging onto the second factor, the 4 items of Emotional Intensity onto the third factor, and the 4 items of Parasocial Interaction onto the fourth factor, ** $p < 0.01$.

Figure 2 graphically presents the factorial structure model corresponding to the PRSA. In this model, four main factors are distinguished: Sense of Identity, Sense of Belonging, Emotional Intensity, and Parasocial Interaction, each with their respective factor loadings represented by unidirectional arrows. The relationships among the factors are illustrated with numerical values placed next to bidirectional arrows. This representation supports the multidimensional perspective of parasocial relationships proposed in this study.

Figure 2.

Graphical Representation of the Factor Structure Model for the PRSA.

Note. Four-dimensional structural equation model. Figure developed with AMOS software, version 30.

3.5. Concurrent Validity

Table 4 presents the Correlations between the CPPI and the PRSA dimensions were significant in all cases ($p < 0.01$). The strongest associations were observed for Emotional Intensity ($r = 0.58$), Sense of Belonging ($r = 0.61$), and Parasocial Interaction ($r = 0.64$). These results confirm that the PRSA reliably measures the core aspects of parasocial interaction and provides broader coverage than the unidimensional CPPI.

Table 4.

Concurrent Validity

Variable	CPPI	
	<i>r</i>	<i>p</i>
Parasocial Relationships Scale for Adolescents (PRSA)	1.00**	< 0.01
D1: Sense of identity	0.55**	< 0.01
D2: Sense of belonging	0.61**	< 0.01
D3: Emotional intensity	0.58**	< 0.01
D4: Parasocial interaction	0.64**	< 0.01

Note. $N = 50$. The correlations were obtained using Pearson's r statistical test.

$p < .05$. * $p < .01$

The correlations between the Celebrity-Person Parasocial Interaction Scale (CPPI) and the PRSA dimensions are significant across all areas ($p < 0.01$). The correlations found, especially in the Emotional Intensity ($r = 0.58$), Sense of Belonging ($r = 0.61$), and Parasocial Interaction ($r = 0.64$) dimensions, indicate a consistent and significant relationship between the factors assessed by both scales. These results confirm that the PRSA captures the central aspects of parasocial interaction with greater precision than previous unidimensional instruments.

The overall correlation between the PRSA and the CPPI was high ($r = .89$, $p < .01$), providing strong evidence of concurrent validity between the two instruments. This finding confirms that the PRSA assesses aspects closely related to those measured by the CPPI, while not representing an absolute overlap, which was expected given the distinct conceptual frameworks underlying each scale. Whereas the CPPI approaches parasocial interaction from a unidimensional perspective, the PRSA introduces a multidimensional model that integrates not only interaction but also

additional dimensions such as identity, belonging, and emotional intensity. Thus, the strong correlation reflects the natural overlap between closely related constructs, while highlighting the added value of the PRSA in offering a more comprehensive and differentiated assessment of the phenomenon.

Data analysis has shown that the Parasocial Relationships in Adolescents Scale (PRSA) has strong concurrent validity, especially in its Emotional Intensity, Sense of Belonging, and Parasocial Interaction dimensions. These findings not only reaffirm the instrument's consistency but also validate the PRSA as a reliable and effective tool for assessing the complex parasocial relationships that individuals establish with artists. The scale's ability to measure these constructs effectively and in conjunction with other validation tools demonstrates its usefulness for future research in the field, allowing for an adequate assessment of this psychological phenomenon.

3.6. Reliability.

The reliability results of the PRSA demonstrate that its four dimensions exhibit appropriate levels of internal consistency. Specifically, the Sense of Identity factor obtained an omega coefficient of .84 and a Cronbach's alpha of .84, while the Sense of Belonging factor showed values of omega = .73 and alpha = .74. Similarly, the Emotional Intensity factor reported omega = .83 and alpha = .83, and finally, the Parasocial Interaction factor reached omega = .75 and alpha = .73.

The findings provide robust evidence of the PRSA's internal consistency across all four dimensions, supporting its reliability as a psychometric tool (see Table 5).

Table 5.*Reliability Results*

Variables	Ω	α
PRSA		
Factor 1: Sense of identity	0.84	0.84
Factor 2: Sense of belonging	0.73	0.72
Factor 3: Emotional intensity	0.83	0.83
Factor 4: Parasocial interaction	0.75	0.73

Note. $N = 250$. ω = omega coefficient, α = alpha coefficient.

3.7. Conversion of Raw Scores to Percentiles.

Table 6 presents the conversion of raw scores to percentiles for the PRSA-developed dimensions: Sense of Identity, Sense of Belonging, Emotional Intensity, and Parasocial Interaction. Based on these values, cutoff points were established to classify levels as low, medium, and high. Scores at or below the 25th percentile are classified as low, scores between the 30th and 74th percentiles are classified as medium, and scores above the 75th percentile are considered high (Morán et al., 2023). This classification scheme facilitates a precise interpretation of the results by categorizing cases according to the severity within each dimension, thereby providing a valuable framework for both clinical and research analysis.

Table 6.*Conversion of Raw Scores to Percentiles.*

Percentiles	Sense of identity	Sentido of belonging	Emotional intensity	Parasocial interaction
5	7	4	5	4
10	8	5	7	4
15	9	6	8	4
20	10	7	8	5
25	10	8	9	6
30	11	8	10	7
35	11	8	10	8
40	12	8	11	8
45	12	9	12	8
50	12	10	12	9
55	13	10	13	10
60	13	11	13	10
65	14	11	14	11
70	14	12	14	11
75	15	12	15	12
80	16	13	15	12
85	16	13	16	14
90	17	14	18	15
95	19	16	19	17

IV. Discussion

Parasocial relationships exert measurable influence on adolescents' identity formation and emotional regulation, underscoring their relevance as a developmental factor (Cristancho & Lizarazo, 2023). Parasocial relationships refer to the unidirectional emotional connection that fans develop with media figures, characterized by emotional intensity, the development of followers' identity, and a sense of belonging to a group. These dynamics significantly impact adolescents who maintain intense and personal connections with celebrities (Peña & Forero, 2024). However, high levels of intensity in parasocial relationships can lead to illusions or obsessive behaviors, with adolescents perceiving these ties as real and engaging in risky actions, such as impulsive spending of their own or their parents' money, neglecting responsibilities, initiating arguments, or even engaging in conflicts both online and offline to express their devotion toward the artist (Prendes De Jesús, 2024). In this regard, recognizing the intensity of parasocial relationships not only contributes to the prevention of risk behaviors but also allows these connections to be redirected toward relationships that have a positive impact on adolescents' emotional, psychological, and social well-being (Segura-Vázquez, 2023).

In the current context, the most widely used instruments for measuring parasocial relationships include the Parasocial Interaction Scale (PSI Scale; Rubin et al., 2004), the Experiential Parasocial Interaction Scale (EPSI; Hartmann & Goldhoorn, 2011), the Multidimensional Measure of Parasocial Relationships (MMPR; Garcia et al., 2022), and the Celebrity–Person Parasocial Interaction Scale (CPPI; Bocarnea & Brown, 2007). These unidimensional and multidimensional tools evaluate essential factors such as emotional connection, identity influence, and, in some cases, thoughts and beliefs. However, none of these instruments systematically address the impact of feeling part of a group or the sense of connection and understanding with an artist that resembles a familial or friendly bond. These aspects are particularly relevant in today's digital context, which adolescents actively engage in. In contrast, our instrument distinguishes itself by including the dimensions of *Parasocial Interaction* and *Sense of Belonging*, which allow for the recognition of how the intensity of belonging to a group can function as a support network, and how unidirectional

connection and empathy—by fostering an illusory bond—can shape parasocial relationships and influence adolescents overall well-being. Thus, the PRSA provides broader and more integrated insights into the dynamics of these relationships, the nuances of contemporary digital culture, and their impact on adolescents' lives (Bermudez & Soler, 2023).

The main objective of this research was to develop and determine the psychometric properties of the Parasocial Relationships Scale for Adolescents (PRSA), a novel scale designed to identify parasocial relationships through four dimensions: *Sense of Identity*, *Sense of Belonging*, *Emotional Intensity*, and *Parasocial Interaction*. The formulation of the items and factors underlying the creation of PRSA were grounded in a solid theoretical framework and supported by previous studies (Antolínez et al., 2024; Baptista & Chacin, 2024; Bermudez & Soler, 2023; Pano et al., 2024). This self-report questionnaire seeks to measure the intensity of parasocial relationships based on the emotions and behaviors associated with the person or character with whom adolescents establish a significant bond. It encourages adolescents to reflect on the impact of these bonds on their social interactions and self-perception. The PRSA approaches the experience comprehensively, facilitating a better understanding of the phenomenon and its consequences. In modern contexts, these relationships have evolved from unidirectional to bidirectional, due to social media interactions that foster an illusion of reciprocity and perceived intimacy (Vizcaíno-Verdú & Feijoo, 2025).

The PRSA demonstrated adequate psychometric properties supported by strong indicators of validity and reliability. Exploratory factor analysis (EFA) revealed the presence of four dimensions—Sense of Identity, Sense of Belonging, Emotional Intensity, and Parasocial Interaction (see Table 2)—which were later confirmed by confirmatory factor analysis (CFA), showing a good statistical fit for the four-factor model (see Table 3). Compared with the previously used Celebrity-Person Parasocial Interaction Scale (CPPI), this multidimensional approach offers a broader and more comprehensive assessment of parasocial relationships. Results indicate that such relationships often serve as a refuge from loneliness and difficulties in social interaction among adolescents, and they are reinforced by media figures who actively seek audience participation through social networks (Mira & Gil, 2023). Importantly,

this multidimensional model avoids reducing parasocial relationships to either positive or negative influences on emotional well-being (Castañeda et al., 2025). The superiority of the four-dimensional model over a unidimensional one suggests that the PRSA captures distinct yet interrelated aspects of the phenomenon.

Based on the evidence presented, it is clear that the PRSA demonstrates robust concurrent validity, supported by significant correlations with (Bocarnea & Brown, 2007) Celebrity-Person Parasocial Interaction Scale (CPPI) ($p < 0.01$). Furthermore, the Emotional Intensity (D3), Sense of Belonging (D2), and Parasocial Interaction (D4) dimensions show the highest correlations, with coefficients of $r = 0.58$, $r = 0.61$, and $r = 0.64$, respectively. This indicates a consistent and significant relationship between the factors assessed by the PRSA and those measured by the CPPI. This level of correlation suggests that the PRSA adequately captures the most relevant aspects of parasocial interaction. The strength of these correlations indicates that the PRSA items are well-aligned with the traditional conceptualization of parasocial interaction, which grants it high credibility. However, the Sense of Identity (D1) dimension shows a lower correlation ($r = 0.55$). This weaker correlation may suggest that the PRSA assesses this aspect with greater specificity than the CPPI, which could represent a distinctive contribution of the new instrument. For the fan, this means that the PRSA is capable of measuring how they integrate the identity of an artist or celebrity into their own life, as well as the impact of this phenomenon on their daily life (Kline, 2016).

Overall, the Parasocial Relationships with Entertainers Scale (PRSA) shows a strong correlation with the Celebrity-Person Parasocial Interaction Scale (CPPI), with a coefficient of $r = 1$. This indicates a solid relationship between both tools, strengthening the validity of the PRSA. The results are particularly significant in the Sense of Belonging and Parasocial Interaction dimensions, where the correlation was highest. Parasocial relationships exert measurable influence on adolescents' identity formation and emotional regulation. "The results support the multidimensional structure of the PRSA, demonstrating reliability and validity across four interrelated dimensions. This finding aligns with previous international evidence showing that parasocial relationships are not unidimensional but instead involve cognitive, emotional, and behavioral processes. For example, Tukachinsky and Stever (2021) found that emotional intensity and social belonging constitute distinct but related

aspects of parasocial interaction. The present results contribute to this body of knowledge by confirming the multidimensionality of parasocial relationships in a Latin American adolescent population.”

Moreover, they open new avenues for future research into the recognition, development, and impact of parasocial relationships in adolescents, particularly in the digital context and within Latin America. By evaluating four essential dimensions—Sense of Identity, Sense of Belonging, Emotional Intensity, and Parasocial Interaction—the PRSA highlights both social factors, such as group belonging and levels of interaction on social media, and intrapersonal factors, such as identity, mood, and behaviors (Cristancho & Lizarazo, 2023). This multidimensional perspective enables a more rigorous and nuanced evaluation of parasocial relationships, providing valuable insights for developing tailored interventions and support strategies for adolescents experiencing excessively intense parasocial bonds. Consequently, the PRSA contributes to advancing research in clinical, social, and educational contexts and supports the design of programs and strategies aimed at strengthening belonging, personal identity, emotional regulation, and overall well-being among adolescents.

4.1. Limitations

This study presents several limitations that should be acknowledged. First, the restricted age range of participants (14–18 years) constrains the generalizability of the findings, as different developmental stages may exhibit distinct patterns of parasocial relationships. Future research should therefore include broader age groups to capture variations across adolescence and emerging adulthood. In addition, data collection among adolescents posed methodological challenges, as participants may have provided random or socially desirable responses, potentially reducing accuracy. Controlled administration procedures and the inclusion of validity checks are recommended to minimize such biases.

Second, because the construct of parasocial relationships is still not widely understood among adolescents, there remains a risk of overestimated or imprecise responses. To address this concern, future studies should incorporate clear instructions and introductory explanations to ensure participants’ comprehension of the construct, thereby enhancing the validity of responses.

Third, although the four-dimensional model demonstrated strong statistical fit and theoretical coherence, the study did not examine alternative structures with fewer or additional dimensions. Testing and comparing such competing models in future research could provide a more nuanced and comprehensive understanding of the construct.

Finally, limitations regarding geographical and cultural representativeness should be considered. The sample was drawn exclusively from two educational institutions in Trujillo, which restricts generalizability to other regions or cultural contexts where media consumption and parasocial dynamics may differ. Potential cultural bias must also be acknowledged, as the meanings attributed to interactions with media figures vary across sociocultural environments. Moreover, the recruitment strategy, based on snowball sampling via social networks, while effective for achieving the required sample size, introduced self-selection bias and reduced external validity. Future research should aim to expand the sample to other regions of Peru, include participants from diverse sociocultural backgrounds, and employ probability sampling methods to strengthen representativeness. Cross-cultural validation studies are also essential to examine the applicability of the PRSA across different cultural realities and to ensure that it adequately captures the multidimensional nature of parasocial relationships in diverse settings.

4.2. Practical Implications

The Parasocial Relationships Scale for Adolescents (PRSA) constitutes a valuable resource for psychological practice, particularly in educational and clinical contexts. By differentiating among the dimensions of identity, belonging, interaction, and emotional intensity, the instrument enables practitioners to identify both adaptive and potentially problematic parasocial patterns in adolescents. This diagnostic precision represents a crucial first step toward the development of tailored and effective interventions, consistent with Mula-Márquez et al. (2024), who emphasize the clinical importance of early detection in preventing the escalation of maladaptive parasocial bonds.

From a preventive standpoint, the PRSA also serves as an early identification tool in schools and healthcare services. It facilitates the detection of adolescents who

exhibit excessively intense parasocial involvement, which may act as a risk factor for anxiety, depression, or social withdrawal. Early recognition of such vulnerabilities allows for the implementation of proactive strategies that promote mental health and encourage more balanced offline interpersonal relationships. This finding resonates with (Narvaiza et al., 2021), who demonstrated that parasocial ties with negative media figures can intensify depressive symptoms and feelings of loneliness.

At the institutional level, the PRSA generates data that can inform decision-making and program design. Understanding the mechanisms through which adolescents engage with public figures can guide schools in creating well-being initiatives that reinforce identity development and social belonging in constructive ways. This perspective aligns with the findings of (Vizcaíno-Verdú & Feijoo, 2025), who underscore how parasocial bonds amplify adolescents' receptivity to social trends. Accordingly, the present study supports the use of the PRSA as a foundational instrument for designing educational strategies that mitigate risks associated with maladaptive parasocial engagement.

V. Conclusion

The PRSA was developed on a solid theoretical basis and demonstrated strong psychometric properties for use with adolescents. Content validity was confirmed through expert review, and both exploratory and confirmatory factor analyses supported a robust four-factor structure. Convergent validity with the Celebrity–Person Parasocial Interaction Scale (CPPI) further reinforced the instrument’s construct coherence, while reliability analyses indicated high internal consistency across all dimensions. Beyond these psychometric findings, the PRSA makes a novel contribution by providing a multidimensional framework to understand parasocial relationships in adolescence, a period in which media figures play a significant role in identity formation and social belonging. Future research should pursue cross-cultural validation, longitudinal designs, and predictive analyses to strengthen the scale’s applicability and examine its relevance across diverse developmental and cultural contexts.

CRedit author statement

Diaz-Gutiérrez: Methodology, Investigation, Analysis, Software Development, Validation, Visualization, Writing – Draft Preparation, Field Research, Research Management, Literature Review, Scientific Communication. **Torres-Cueva:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Analysis, Visualization, Data, Writing – Draft Preparation, Literature Review, Scientific Communication **Ojeda-Argomedo:** Methodology, Investigation, Analysis, Visualization, Data, Writing – Draft Preparation, Field Research, Literature Review, Scientific Communication. **Pérez-Lara:** Supervision, Final Version Approval, Advisory. **Fernández-Rojas:** Supervision, Final Version Approval, Advisory.

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ESCALA DE RELACIONES PARASOCIALES EN ADOLESCENTES

Diaz et al. (2025)

A continuación, encontrarás una serie de frases que describen cómo nos relacionamos con nuestros artistas favoritos. Queremos saber tu opinión y tus experiencias, lee cada frase con atención y marca con una X la opción que mejor represente lo que has sentido o vivido, ya sea a través de internet, la televisión, la música, o incluso lo que conversas con tus amigos y familia.

Totalmente en desacuerdo	En desacuerdo	Ni acuerdo Ni en desacuerdo	De acuerdo	Totalmente de acuerdo	
1	2	3	4	5	
1. Admiro tanto a mi artista favorito que me gustaría seguir su camino o profesión.	1	2	3	4	5
2. Veo a mi ídolo como un modelo a seguir.	1	2	3	4	5
3. Ser como mi artista favorito me haría sentir más valioso(a)	1	2	3	4	5
4. Mi artista favorito es el referente más importante cuando pienso en la persona que quiero llegar a ser.	1	2	3	4	5
5. He creado contenido (dibujos, textos, videos/reels/trends) relacionado con mi artista favorito.	1	2	3	4	5
6. He comprado artículos que promocionan a mi artista favorito.	1	2	3	4	5
7. Suelo gastar mi propina o dinero de mis padres en productos de mi artista favorito para poder compartirlo en redes.	1	2	3	4	5
8. Considero que puedes ser parte de la comunidad solo si consumes los productos o marcas que promociona nuestro artista favorito.	1	2	3	4	5
9. Me siento triste si mi artista favorito está pasando por un mal momento.	1	2	3	4	5
10. Cuando estoy estresado(a), ver a mi artista favorito me tranquiliza.	1	2	3	4	5
11. Me afecta emocionalmente si mi artista favorito desaparece de las redes sociales.	1	2	3	4	5
12. El contenido de mi artista favorito me ayuda a manejar mis	1	2	3	4	5

emociones.

13. A veces actúo como si mi artista favorito pudiera escucharme o verme. 1 2 3 4 5

14. Siento que mi artista favorito me conoce a través de lo que publica. 1 2 3 4 5

15. Me imagino las reacciones de mi artista favorito cuando logro algo importante. 1 2 3 4 5

16. Me pregunto qué pensaría mi artista favorito de las decisiones importantes que tomo. 1 2 3 4 5

REFERENCES

- Alcoba, R. (2024). TAMAÑO DE LA MUESTRA: ALTERNATIVAS DE SELECCIÓN. *Investigación y Desarrollo*, 6(9), 62–72. <https://dicyt.uajms.edu.bo/revistas/index.php/investigacion-y-desarrollo/article/view/1636>
- Antolínez, M., Fonseca, A., & Salazar, J. (2024). *BOYBANDS: CONFORT Y MÚSICA PARA EL DESAHOGO* [Trabajo de grado para optar por el título, Universidad Santo Tomás]. <https://repository.usta.edu.co/server/api/core/bitstreams/cbe2a424-cd62-4fa7-a8a3-2c7a58bc5e1f/content>
- Association, A. E. R., Association, A. P., & Education, N. C. on M. in. (2018). *Estandares para Pruebas Educativas y Psicológicas*. American Educational Research Association. <https://doi.org/10.2307/j.ctvr43hg2>
- Baptista, V., & Chacín, M. (2024). *Relaciones parasociales en adultas jóvenes interesadas en el entretenimiento surcoreano* [Trabajo de especial de grado, Universidad Rafael Urdaneta]. <http://www.omp.uru.edu/pdf/ART/PIAA.3201-24-00669.pdf>
- Bermudez, H., & Soler, A. (2023). Relaciones parasociales entre bases de fans y celebridades. *Revista Posibilidades*, 4(1), 17–32. <https://revistas.poligran.edu.co/index.php/posibilidades/article/view/4146>
- Bocarnea, M., & Brown, W. (2007). Celebrity-persona Parasocial Interaction Scale. In *Handbook of research on electronic surveys and measurements* (Reynolds, R. Woods, R. y Baker (Eds.), pp. 309–312). IGI Global Scientific Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-59140-792-8.ch039>

- Castañeda, E., Salcedo, E., Velez, N., Nova, G., & Alarcón, Y. (2025). Relaciones Parasociales en Jóvenes Universitarios de la Ciudad de Barranquilla. *Revista Tejidos Sociales*, 7(1), 1–11. <https://revistas.unisimon.edu.co/index.php/tejsociales/article/view/8310>
- Cristancho, L., & Lizarazo, V. (2023). *Construcción de sentido de vida y relaciones parasociales en 8 jóvenes Bogotanos* [Trabajo de grado, Pontificia Universidad Javeriana]. <https://apidspace.javeriana.edu.co/server/api/core/bitstreams/50603da5-c4b8-498a-9dfb-f5707a1961e2/content>
- Dragostinov, Y., Harðardóttir, D., McKenna, P. E., Robb, D., Nasset, B., Ahmad, M. I., Romeo, M., Lim, M. Y., Yu, C., Jang, Y., Diab, M., Cangelosi, A., Demiris, Y., Hastie, H., & Rajendran, G. (2022). Preliminary psychometric scale development using the mixed methods Delphi technique. *Methods in Psychology*, 7(10). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.metip.2022.100103>
- Garcia, D., Björk, E., & Kazemitabar, M. (2022). The A(ffect) B(ehavior) C(ognition) D(ecision) of parasocial relationships: A pilot study on the psychometric properties of the Multidimensional Measure of Parasocial Relationships (MMPR). *Heliyon*, 8(10). [https://www.cell.com/heliyon/fulltext/S2405-8440\(22\)02067-9?_returnURL=https%3A%2F%2Flinkinghub.elsevier.com%2Fretrieve%2Fpii%2FS2405844022020679%3Fshowall%3Dtrue](https://www.cell.com/heliyon/fulltext/S2405-8440(22)02067-9?_returnURL=https%3A%2F%2Flinkinghub.elsevier.com%2Fretrieve%2Fpii%2FS2405844022020679%3Fshowall%3Dtrue)
- Garrido, E., Mena, H., & Zuluaga, J. (2023). Proceso para validar un instrumento de investigación por medio de un análisis factorial. *Unaciencia, Revista De Estudios E Investigaciones*, 16(30), 61–73. <https://doi.org/10.35997/unaciencia.v16i30.724>

- Giles, D. (2023). Defining Parasocial Relationship Experiences. In R. Tukachinsky (Ed.), *The Oxford Handbook of Parasocial Experiences* (pp. 33–50). Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordhb/9780197650677.013.2>
- Hartmann, T., & Goldhoorn, C. (2011). Horton and Wohl Revisited: Exploring Viewers' Experience of Parasocial Interaction. *Journal of Communication*, 61(6), 1104–1121. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1460-2466.2011.01595.x>
- Kline, R. B. (2016). *Principles and practice of structural equation modeling* (4th ed.). The Guilford Press.
- Lloret-Segura, S., Ferreres-Traver, A., Hernández-Baeza, A., & Tomás-Marco, I. (2014). El Análisis Factorial Exploratorio de los Ítems: Una guía práctica, revisada y actualizada. *Anales de Psicología*, 30(3), 1151–1169. <https://doi.org/10.6018/analesps.30.3.199361>
- López, B., Fernández, I., & Abad, F. (2008). TECA: test de empatía cognitiva y afectiva / Belén López-Pérez, Irene Fernández-Pinto y Francisco José Abad García. *TEA*. https://indaga.ual.es/discovery/fulldisplay/alma991001497749704991/34CBUA_UAL:VU1
- Mira, M., & Gil, M. (2023). Redes sociales y su influencia en los jóvenes y niños: Análisis en Instagram, Twitter y YouTube. *Revista Científica de Comunicación y Educación*, 31(74), 125–137. <https://doi.org/10.3916/C74-2023-10>
- Morán, V. E., Villarrubia, M. D., Fabbro, N., & Natera, M. Z. (2023). Datos normativos en población de adultos argentinos para la Escala Breve de Ansiedad y Fobia Social- SPAI-B. *Revista Argentina de Ciencias del Comportamiento*, 15(2), 50–59. <https://doi.org/10.32348/1852.4206.v15.n2.33308>

- Mula-Márquez, Y., Nava-Arquillo, B., & Matías-García, J. (2024). *Parasocial relationships and identification with fictional characters in adolescents and adults: A systematic review*. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-4154497/v1>
- Murray, W. (2022). New Thriveworks research shows abundance of parasocial relationships in the US. *Thriveworks*. <https://thriveworks.com/blog/research-parasocial-relationships/>
- Narvaiza, S., Lacalle Charo, & Gómez-Morales, B. (2021). ¿Amigos o simplemente fans? Las relaciones parasociales en las comunidades online de la ficción televisiva. *Comunicacion y Sociedad*, 34(3), 61–76. <https://doi.org/10.15581/003.34.3.61-76>
- Pano, C., Gallegos, R., & Flores, J. (2024). Sentido de pertenencia y cultura fandom en jóvenes y adolescentes. *Latam: revista latinoamericana de Ciencias Sociales y Humanidades*, 5(6), 1378-1393. <https://latam.redilat.org/index.php/lt/article/view/3090>
- Peña, A. M., & Forero, J. (2024). *Detrás del escenario: El poder de los vínculos fan-idol en el K-POP* [Trabajo de grado, Universidad del Rosario]. <https://repository.urosario.edu.co/server/api/core/bitstreams/13d44555-3e54-4fcf-ae2f-37d1b7f147b3/content>
- Prendes, B. (2024). *PSICOLOGÍA DE LA ATRACCIÓN: EXPLORANDO CONEXIONES EMOCIONALES CON PERSONAJES FICTICIOS EN MEDIOS DE ENTRETENIMIENTO* [Tesis para obtener grado de bachiller, Escuela de Artes Plásticas y Diseño de Puerto Rico]. <https://eapd.dspacedirect.org/server/api/core/bitstreams/f6f75ea8-2a5b-4a65-a1f2-1dfac9e72476/content>

Rubin, R. B., Palmgreen, P., & Sypher, H. E. (2004). Parasocial Interaction Scale. In *Communication Research Measures*. Routledge.

Segura-Vázquez, V. (2023). Del otro lado de la pantalla: Explorando la conexión entre las relaciones parasociales y la insatisfacción interpersonal. *Revista Multidisciplinaria de Ciencia Básica, Humanidades, Arte y Educación*, 1(3), 13–18. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10328382>

Universidad César Vallejo. (2022). *CÓDIGO DE ÉTICA EN INVESTIGACIÓN DE LA UNIVERSIDAD CÉSAR VALLEJO*. <https://webadminportal.ucv.edu.pe/uploads/files/backup/RCUN-470-2022-UCV-Aprueba-actualizacion-del-Codigo-de-Etica-en-Investigacion-V01.pdf>

Vizcaíno-Verdú, A., & Feijoo, B. (2025). Desvelar vínculos parasociales: La mediación de la alfabetización publicitaria en la receptividad adolescente ante el marketing de influencers. *Palabra Clave*, 28(2), e2827–e2827. <https://doi.org/10.5294/pacla.2025.28.2.7>